

A Study on The Impact of Academic Interventions on Plant Blindness Among Students of Higher Education

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Abstract

Plant blindness, the tendency to overlook or undervalue the significance of plants in the environment, poses a critical challenge to biodiversity conservation and ecological understanding. This study investigates the effectiveness of educational interventions in addressing plant blindness among college students across colleges of India. Utilizing a quasi-experimental design, the intervention aims to enhance plant awareness through interactive learning activities. Pre- and post-intervention assessments measure changes in knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours towards plants. The study also examines demographic factors influencing intervention outcomes. Results indicate significant improvements in plant awareness post-intervention, highlighting the importance of experiential learning in environmental education. Addressing plant blindness is essential for promoting environmental stewardship and biodiversity conservation.

Keywords

Plant Blindness, Environmental Education, Educational Intervention, Biodiversity Conservation, College Students.

Introduction

The concept of 'plant blindness' is a critical issue that demands immediate attention in the field of contemporary environmental education. This term, 'plant blindness', is used to describe a cognitive bias where individuals, more often than not, tend to ignore or underestimate the significance of plants in their immediate and extended surroundings. Instead, they choose to focus their attention on organisms that are more noticeable or charismatic, such as animals or birds (Wandersee & Schussler, 2001). This bias, subtle yet pervasive, has far-reaching implications for various crucial areas such as the conservation of biodiversity, the health and sustainability of ecosystems, and the global efforts towards achieving sustainable development goals.

When individuals overlook the importance of plants, they inadvertently fail to acknowledge their vital and multifaceted role in maintaining life on Earth. Plants are the primary producers in most ecosystems, providing oxygen, a fundamental requirement for most life forms. They are also a key source of food, offering a variety of nutrients necessary for survival. Moreover, numerous plants have medicinal properties, providing resources for traditional and modern medicines. Additionally, plants serve as habitats, offering shelter and breeding grounds for a multitude of organisms. This lack of recognition and appreciation for plants can undermine conservation initiatives, leading to further ecological degradation. It can result in the loss of biodiversity, disruption of ecosystems, and even contribute to climate change (Kelley & Dwyer, 2020).

Therefore, it is of utmost importance to address plant blindness through specific, targeted educational interventions. These interventions aim to cultivate a deeper understanding and appreciation of plants among the general public. By doing so, they encourage

environmental stewardship, promoting actions that respect and protect the environment. Ultimately, these efforts contribute to the conservation of biodiversity, ensuring the survival and well-being of all life forms on our planet.

Aim of study

This study aims to assess an educational intervention's effectiveness in combating plant blindness among Indian college students by enhancing awareness, knowledge and appreciation of plants. It seeks to determine current plant awareness levels, evaluate intervention impact, explore attitudes and behaviours towards plants pre- and post-intervention, and investigate demographic factors' influence on intervention efficacy.

Review of Literature

The historical attitudes towards plants, tracing back from the early days of human civilization to the current era marked by rapid urbanization and technological advancements, provide a rich context to the phenomenon of plant blindness (Kelley & Dwyer, 2020). In traditional societies, plants were not just seen as passive elements of the environment, but were held in high regard for their medicinal properties and cultural importance. They were integral to the daily lives of people, providing food, medicine, and materials for shelter and clothing.

However, with the advent of modern lifestyles, marked by urban living and technological advancements, there has been a growing detachment from nature (Schultz, 2002). This shift has led to a decrease in direct interactions with plants and a lack of understanding of their crucial role in our ecosystems and lives. Numerous research studies have delved deep into the prevalence and implications of plant blindness, exploring the various factors contributing to it and its impact on environmental attitudes (Wandersee & Clary, 2006; Price, 2010). Factors such as limited exposure to nature due to urban living, inadequate formal education about plants in our schooling systems, and anthropocentric biases that prioritize human needs and perspectives have been identified as significant contributors to plant blindness (Wandersee & Schussler, 2001).

Furthermore, studies have underscored the correlation between awareness of plants and pro-environmental behaviours (Balmford et al., 2002). This suggests that increasing plant awareness could be a key strategy in promoting sustainable behaviours and attitudes. In response to this, interventions designed to combat plant blindness have been developed. These include hands-on activities that allow individuals to interact directly with plants, and multimedia approaches that leverage technology to engage and educate (Wandersee & Schussler, 2001; Balmford et al., 2002). These interventions have shown promising results in enhancing plant awareness and shifting attitudes towards plants.

Educational initiatives like visits to botanical gardens and interactive learning programs have also proven effective in augmenting plant knowledge and fostering positive attitudes towards plants (Davies et al., 2009). These initiatives provide immersive experiences that allow individuals to appreciate the beauty and complexity of plants, thereby combating plant blindness and promoting a deeper connection with nature.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental research design was utilized to compare the effectiveness of an intervention aimed at remedying plant blindness. This design comprised an experimental group, which received the intervention, and a control group that did not (Campbell & Stanley, 1963).

Data collection was conducted via Google Forms, chosen for its user-friendly interface and comprehensive features, ensuring the reliability and validity of the collected data. Participants were drawn from a diverse range of educational institutions, encompassing both urban and rural settings, thus providing a varied and representative sample. (chart 1)

The intervention sought to bolster awareness, knowledge, and appreciation of plants through interactive lectures, hands-on activities like plant identification and collection visits, multimedia presentations, and group discussions. (Chart 2)

Data collection encompassed both quantitative and qualitative methods. Pre- and post-intervention surveys gauged changes in knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours, while focus group discussions and semi-structured interviews provided detailed insights into participants' experiences and perceptions.

Quantitative data underwent analysis using statistical software, while qualitative data from focus groups and interviews was also analysed.

Statistics Used in the Study

The study included a total of 450 students, with 220 from rural colleges and 230 from urban colleges. The quantitative findings from pre- and post-intervention surveys revealed significant improvements in knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours related to plants for the experimental group compared to the control group. (Table 1)

The qualitative findings from focus group discussions and semi-structured interviews supported the quantitative results. Thematic analysis revealed key themes of enhanced awareness and appreciation of plants, engagement and enjoyment of the intervention activities, and positive behavioural changes towards plants. (Table 2)

Result and Discussion

The intervention effectively improved plant awareness among college students in study, evidenced by significant increases in knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours towards plants. Both rural and urban students benefited from the intervention, indicating its broad applicability.

This study underscores the importance of integrating hands-on, interactive learning activities into higher education curricula to combat plant blindness. Such initiatives can enhance student engagement, critical thinking, and environmental stewardship.

This study confirms the efficacy of interactive learning in enhancing environmental awareness, aligning with findings by Sanders et al. (2014) and Krasny and Tidball (2009). By addressing plant blindness, it fills a gap in the literature. Supporting both rural and urban students, it provides a replicable model for global interventions,

echoing Dwyer et al.'s (1992) conclusions on nature-based education's effectiveness.

Appendices

1.Survey/Interview Questions

- a.What is your current level of knowledge about plants?
- b.How often do you engage with plants in your daily life?
- c.What are your attitudes towards plants and their importance in the environment?
- d.Have you participated in any plant-related activities before? If so, please describe.
- e.What is the importance of educational intervention to correct the neglect of the importance of plants?
- fHow do you think the intervention has impacted your knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours towards plants?

Data Tables

Quantitative Findings (table 1)

Group	Location	N	Pre- Intervention Knowledge Score (Mean ± SD)	Post- Intervention Knowledge Score (Mean ± SD)	Pre- Intervention Attitude Score (Mean ± SD)	Post- Intervention Attitude Score (Mean ± SD)	Pre- Intervention Behaviour Score (Mean ± SD)	Post- Intervention Behaviour Score (Mean ± SD)
Exp 1	Rural	110	45.2±10.5	81.0±9.6	2.8±0.8	4.7±0.5	3.4±1.3	8.0±1.2
Exp 2	Urban	120	45.9±9.9	80.0±10.1	3.0±0.8	4.5±0.6	3.6±1.2	7.6±1.3
Control	Rural	110	45.5±10.1	47.0±10.2	2.9±0.7	3.0±0.7	3.5±1.1	3.6±1.1
Control	Urban	120	46.7±9.8	49.4±10.0	3.1±0.7	3.2±0.8	3.7±1.1	3.9±1.2

Qualitative Findings (table 2)

Theme	Location	Representative Quotes
Enhanced Awareness and Appreciation	Rural	"I never realized how essential plants are to our environment and health. The activities made me see plants in a new light."
	Urban	"The multimedia presentations and hands-on activities really opened my eyes to the beauty and necessity of plants."
Engagement and Enjoyment	Rural	"The plant identification exercises were fun and educational. It was great to learn by actually seeing and touching the plants."
	Urban	"Group discussions helped us share ideas and learn from each other. It was a refreshing way to learn."
Behavioral Changes	Rural	"I have started a small garden at home. It's rewarding to see the plants grow."
	Urban	"I've begun visiting the botanical garden regularly. It's now one of my favorite places."

Conclusion

This study underscores the efficacy of interventions in addressing plant blindness among college students, highlighting the significance of experiential learning in higher education. Significant enhancements in plant awareness were evident across both rural and urban student cohorts, particularly through hands-on activities and multimedia presentations. Moving forward, future research should delve into the long-term effects of such interventions and explore optimal integration strategies into higher education curricula, accounting for diverse demographic and geographical contexts. The practical implications of this study suggest that implementing similar interventions can substantially augment environmental education in colleges, cultivating a deeper understanding and appreciation of plants among students and fostering environmental stewardship efforts.

Limitation of the Study

The quasi-experimental design, limited sample from selected colleges of India, and short-term intervention hinder generalizability. Potential biases include selection bias, social desirability bias, and researcher involvement.

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